

CHEMICAL STUDY OF THE SEEDS OF SARDA

By S. ALI AHMAD AND D. R. DHINGRA

Component fatty acids of Sarda (Melon) seed oil excluding unsaponifiable matter (N-S) are myristic (2.0%), palmitic (2.0%), stearic (5.5%), arachidic (0.9), oleic (32.9%), linoleic (55.5%); N-S is 0.6%. The acids seem to be evenly distributed in the glycerides.

Sarda, a variety of *Cucumis melo*, Linn. (melon) grows abundantly in Afghanistan and Baluchistan. Its fruits and seeds are somewhat different in taste and bigger in size than those of the Punjab Kharbuz or melon (*cf.* Dhingra and Narain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 123). Component fatty acids of Sarda seed fat and other constituents of their seeds have been examined and compared with those of Kharbuz seeds, with respect to varietal, climatic and soil differences.

Kernels contain 44.6% oil, 35.8% proteinous substances, 3.0% phosphates (P_2O_5), 5.6% ash. Thus they form a good substitution for the more expensive almond seed kernels, as an article of nourishing food. Oil also is of a pleasant odour and taste and light pale colour and can be used medicinally and as an article of food in place of the highly expensive almond oil.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sarda seeds were obtained from Quetta (Baluchistan) and oil from it was extracted with light petroleum ether. The data of the chemical examination of its seeds and fat are as follows :—

Seeds :	Moisture (9.0%), proteinous substances (25.2%), oil (24.9%).
Kernels :	Oil (44.6%), proteinous substances (35.8%), phosphates (P_2O_5 , 3.0%); ash (5.6%) (ash contains iron, potassium, silica, phosphates and traces of calcium).
Oil :	Sp. gr. at 23.5°, 0.9174; Sap. equiv., 294.3; I.V. 125.5; A.V. 3.9; refractive index n_D^{20} 0.4863; N-S., 0.6%.

Corresponding data of the Punjab Melon seed (*loc. cit.*) are :

Kernels :	Oil (40.0%), proteinous substances (22.8%), phosphates (P_2O_5), 0.3%.
Oil :	S.E., 270.0; I.V., 117.1; A.V., 0.9; N-S, 0.8%

Thus Sarda seed kernels form a source of richer food in every respect than those of Kharbuz kernels.

Component Fatty Acids

The oil (450 g.) was subjected to a detailed examination for their component fatty acids and the presence of these acids was confirmed according to the methods given in the study of Kharbuz oil (*loc. cit.*). Their final data along with those of the Kharbuz oil and Californian melon oil (Baughmann and Jamieson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 152) are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Cucumis melo seed oil

Acids.	Sarda (Baluchistan)	Kharbuz (Punjab)	Melon Californian (Cantaloup)
Caproic	—	1.0	—
Caprylic	—	2.0	—
Myristic	2.0	1.3	0.3
Palmitic	3.2	7.2	10.3
Stearic	5.4	0.2	4.6
Arachidic	0.9	—	—
Oleic	32.7	42.7	27.5
Linoleic	55.2	44.8	57.3
N-S	0.6	0.9	—
Association ratio (i.e., mols. unsaturated : mols. saturated acids)	7.21 : 1	5.62 : 1	—

From the above data, it is clear that the component acids of Baluchistan Sarda seed oil differ to some extent from the other two melon seed fats. Lower acids (caproic and caprylic) are found in the Punjab oil only but these are compensated by the higher percentage of higher saturated acids (stearic and arachidic) in the other two fats. Moreover, more highly unsaturated acid (linoleic) preponderates in Sarda oil like that in Californian oil. It seems that the soil and climate and varietal differences affect the metabolism of fats in seeds. Cold, dry climate and rocky dry soil of Quetta (Baluchistan) seem to help in the production of higher percentage of saturated acids of higher molecular weight and more highly unsaturated acids than the hot, somewhat humid climate and soft, alluvial soil of the Punjab. However, there is no fundamental difference in the two fats and there is a broad similarity in their having almost the same percentage of total unsaturated acids (about 88%) which preponderate and are characteristic of Cucurbitaceae family (Hilditch, *Allgem. Oel Fett. Ztg.*, 1930, 27, 184 219, 255).

Component Glycerides.—No fully saturated glycerides separated on cooling the acetone solution of the fat at 5° for five days.